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THE CLOUD COMPUTING SECURITY AND ISSUES

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Abstract: Cloud computing is a complete internet dependent technology where client data is stored and maintain in the data center of a cloud provider. Cloud computing is architecture for providing computing service via the internet on demand and Pay- Per-Use access to a pool of shared resources namely networks, storage, servers, services and applications, without physically acquiring them. So it saves managing cost and time for organizations. The security for Cloud Computing is emerging area for study and this paper provide security topic in terms of cloud computing based on analysis of Cloud Security treat sand Technical Components of Cloud Computing.

Keywords: Cloud, Services, Cloud service user, SAAS, PAAS, IAAS, Public cloud, Private cloud, Hybrid cloud, Security Issues, License Risk.

I. INTRODUCTION

The cloud computing is a new computing model which comes from grid computing, distributed computing, parallel computing, virtualization technology, utility computing and other computer technologies and it has more advantage characters such as large scale computation and data storage, virtualization, high expansibility, high reliability and low price service. The security problem of cloud computing is very important and it can prevent the rapid development of cloud computing. This paper introduces some cloud computing systems and analyzes cloud computing security problem and its strategy according to the cloud computing concepts and characters. The data privacy and service availability in cloud computing are the key security problem. Single security method cannot solve the cloud computing security problem and many traditional and new technologies and strategies must be used together for protecting the total cloud computing system.

Fig.1 General Representation of cloud

We are conducting research on secure cloud computing .Due to the extensive complexity of the cloud; we contend that it will be difficult to provide a holistic solution to secure the cloud at present. Therefore our goal is to make increment enhancements to securing the cloud that will ultimately result in a secure cloud. In particular, we are developing a secure cloud consisting of hardware, software and data. Our cloud system will

- support efficient storage of encrypted sensitive data
- store, manage and query massive amounts of data
- support fine grained access control and
- Support strong authentication.

II. ARCHITECTURE OF CLOUD COMPUTING

Front End

The front end is used by the client. It contains client-side interfaces and applications that are required to access the cloud computing platforms. The front end includes web servers (including Chrome, Firefox, internet explorer, etc.), thin & fat clients, tablets, and mobile devices.

Fig.2 Architecture of cloud computing

Back End

The back end is used by the service provider. It manages all the resources that are required to provide cloud computing services. It includes a huge amount of data storage, security mechanism, virtual machines, deploying models, servers, traffic control mechanisms, etc.

Components of Cloud Computing Architecture

There are the following components of cloud computing architecture -

1. Client Infrastructure

Client Infrastructure is a Front end component. It provides GUI (Graphical User Interface) to interact with the cloud.

2. Application

The application may be any software or platform that a client wants to access.

3. Service

A Cloud Services manages that which type of service you access according to the client's requirement.

Cloud computing offers the following three type of services:

i. Software as a Service (SaaS) – It is also known as **cloud application services**. Mostly, SaaS applications run directly through the web browser means we do not require to download and install these applications. Some important example of SaaS is given below –

Example: Google Apps, Salesforce Dropbox, Slack, Hubspot, Cisco WebEx.

ii. Platform as a Service (PaaS) – It is also known as **cloud platform services**. It is quite similar to SaaS, but the difference is that PaaS provides a platform for software creation, but using SaaS, we can access software over the internet without the need of any platform.

Example: Windows Azure, Force.com, Magento Commerce Cloud, OpenShift.

iii. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) – It is also known as **cloud infrastructure services**. It is responsible for managing applications data, middleware, and runtime environments.

Example: Amazon Web Services (AWS) EC2, Google Compute Engine (GCE), Cisco Metapod.

4. Runtime Cloud

Runtime Cloud provides the **execution and runtime environment** to the virtual machines.

5. Storage

Storage is one of the most important components of cloud computing. It provides a huge amount of storage capacity in the cloud to store and manage data.

6. Infrastructure

It provides services on the **host level**, **application level**, and **network level**. Cloud infrastructure includes hardware and software components such as servers, storage, network devices, virtualization software, and other storage resources that are needed to support the cloud computing model.

7. Management

Management is used to manage components such as application, service, runtime cloud, storage, infrastructure, and other security issues in the backend and establish coordination between them.

8. Security

Security is an in-built back end component of cloud computing. It implements a security mechanism in the back end.

9. Internet

The Internet is medium through which front end and back end can interact and communicate with each other.

III. SECURITY SUBSYSTEM

The five functional security subsystems defined by IBM are as follows:

Audit and Compliance:

This subsystem addresses the data collection, analysis, and archival requirements in meeting standards of proof for an IT environment. It captures, analyzes, reports, archives, and retrieves records of events and conditions during the operation of the system .

Access Control:

This subsystem enforces security policies by gating access to processes and services within a computing solution via identification, authentication, and authorization [5]. In the context of cloud computing, all of these mechanisms must also be considered from the view of a federated access control system.

Flow Control:

This subsystem enforces security policies by gating information flow and visibility and ensuring information integrity within a computing solution.

Identity and Credential Management:

This subsystem creates and manages identity and permission objects that describe access rights information across network sand among the subsystems, platforms, and processes, in a computing solution [4]. It may be required to adhere to legal criteria for creation and maintenance of credential objects.

Solution Integrity:

This subsystem addresses the requirement for reliable and proper operation of a computing solution

IV.CLOUD MODELS

Four different cloud deployment models namely Private cloud, Public cloud, Hybrid cloud and Community cloud.

Private cloud:

Private cloud can be owned or leased and managed by the organization or a third party and exist at on-premises or off- premises. It is more expensive and secure when compared to public cloud. In private cloud there are no additional security regulations, legal requirements or bandwidth limitations that can be present in a public cloud environment, by using a private cloud, the cloud service providers and the clients

have optimized control of the infrastructure and improved security, since user's access and the networks used are restricted. One of the best examples of a private cloud is Eucalyptus Systems.

Public Cloud:

A cloud infrastructure is provided to many customers and is managed by a third party and exists beyond the company firewall. Multiple enterprises can work on the infrastructure provided, at the same time and users can dynamically provision resources. These clouds are fully hosted and managed by the cloud provider and fully responsibilities of installation, management, provisioning, and maintenance. Customers are only charged for the resources they use, so under-utilization is eliminated. Since consumers have little control over the infrastructure, processes requiring powerful security and regulatory compliance are not always a good fit for public clouds. In this model, no access restrictions can be applied and no authorization and authentication techniques can be used. Public cloud providers such as Google or Amazon offer an access control to their clients. Examples of a public cloud include Microsoft Azure, Google App Engine.

Hybrid Cloud:

A composition of two or more cloud deployment models, linked in a way that data transfer takes place between them without affecting each other. These clouds would typically be created by the enterprise and management responsibilities would be split between the enterprise and the cloud provider.

In this model, a company can outline the goals and needs of services. A well-constructed hybrid cloud can be useful for providing secure services such as receiving customer payments, as well as those that are secondary to the business, such as employee payroll processing. The major drawback to the hybrid cloud is the difficulty in

effectively creating and governing such a solution. Services from different sources must be obtained and provisioned as if they originated from a single location, and interactions between private and public components can make the implementation even more complicated. These can be private, community or public clouds which are linked by a proprietary or standard technology that provides portability of data and applications among the composing clouds. An example of a Hybrid Cloud includes Amazon Web Services (AWS).

Community Cloud:

Infrastructure shared by several organizations for a shared cause and may be managed by them or a third party service provider and rarely offered cloud model.

These clouds are normally based on an agreement between related business organizations such as banking or educational organizations. A cloud environment operating according to this model may exist locally or remotely

V. SECURITY GUIDANCE

General security guidance to deal with the above threats can be found in :

- **Encryption and Key Management:** Encryption provides data protection while key management enables access to protected data. It is strongly recommended to encrypt data in transit over networks, at rest, and on backup media. In particular, data encryption at rest (e.g., for long-term archival storage) can avoid the risk of malicious cloud service providers or malicious multi-tenants abuse. At the same time, secure key stores (including key backup and recoverability) and access to key stores must be securely implemented since improper (or access to) key storage could lead to the compromise of all encrypted data.

- Identity and Access Management: Secure management of identity and access control is a critical factor to prevent account and service hijacking. It is strongly recommended to prohibit sharing of account credentials, to leverage strong (multi-factor) authentication if possible, and to consider delegated authentication and managing trust across all types of cloud services.

VI. SECURITY ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

- Virtual Machine Security
- Network Security
- Data Security
- Data Privacy
- Data Integrity
- Data Location
- Data Availability

Virtual Machine Security:

Virtualization is one of the main components of a cloud. Virtual machines are dynamic i.e it can quickly be reverted to previous instances, paused and restarted, relatively easily. Ensuring that different instances running on the same physical machine are isolated from each other is a major task of virtualization. They can also be readily cloned and seamlessly moved between physical servers. This dynamic nature and potential for VM sprawl makes it difficult to achieve and maintain consistent security. Vulnerabilities or configuration errors may be unknowingly propagated. Also, it is difficult to maintain an auditable record of the security state of a virtual machine at any given point in time. Full Virtualization and Para Virtualization are two kinds of virtualization in a cloud computing paradigm. In full virtualization, entire hardware architecture is replicated virtually. However, in para-virtualization, an operating system is modified so that it can be run concurrently with other operating systems. VMM (Virtual Machine Monitor), is a software layer that abstracts the physical resources used by the multiple virtual machines. The VMM provides a virtual processor

and other virtualized versions of system devices such as I/O devices, storage, memory, etc. Many bugs have been found in all popular VMMs that allow escaping from Virtual machine. Vulnerability in Microsoft Virtual PC and Microsoft Virtual Server could allow a guest operating system user to run code on the host or another guest operating system. Vulnerability was found in VMware's shared folders mechanism that grants users of a guest system read and write access to any portion of the host's file system including the system folder and other security-sensitive files. Vulnerability in Xen can be exploited by "root" users of a guest domain to execute arbitrary commands. The other issue is the control of administrator on host and guest operating systems. Current VMMs (Virtual Machine Monitor) do not offer perfect isolation. Virtual machine monitor should be 'root secure', meaning that no privilege within the virtualized guest environment permits interference with the host system.

Network Security:

Networks are classified into many types like shared and non- shared, public or private, small area or large area networks and each of them have a number of security threats to deal with. Problems associated with the network level security comprise of DNS attacks, Sniffer attacks, issue of reused IP address, etc which are explained in details as follows.

A Domain Name Server (DNS) server performs the translation of a domain name to an IP address. Since the domain names are much easier to remember. Hence, the DNS servers are needed. But there are cases when having called the server by name, the user has been routed to some other evil cloud instead of the one he asked for and hence using IP address is not always feasible. Although using DNS security measures like: Domain Name System Security Extensions (DNSSEC) reduces the effects of DNS threats but still there are cases when these security measures prove to be inadequate when the path between a sender and a receiver gets rerouted through some evil connection. It may happen that

even after all the DNS security measures are taken, still the route selected between the sender and receiver cause security problems [7].

Sniffer attacks are launched by applications that can capture packets flowing in a network and if the data that is being transferred through these packets is not encrypted, it can be read and there are chances that vital information flowing across the network can be traced or captured. A sniffer program, through the NIC (Network Interface Card) ensures that the data/traffic linked to other systems on the network also gets recorded. It can be achieved by placing the NIC in promiscuous mode and in promiscuous mode it can track all data, flowing on the same network. A malicious sniffing detection platform based on ARP (address resolution protocol) and RTT (round trip time) can be used to detect a sniffing system running on a network.

Reused IP address issue has been a big network security concern. When a particular user moves out of a network then the IP-address associated with him (earlier) is assigned to a new user. This sometimes risks the security of the new user as there is a certain time lag between the change of an IP address in DNS and the clearing of that address in DNS caches. And hence, we can say that sometimes though the old IP address is being assigned to a new user still the chances of accessing the data by some other user is not negligible as the address still exists in the DNS cache and the data belonging to a particular user may become accessible to some other user violating the privacy of the original user .

Data security:

For general user, it is quite easy to find the possible storage on the side that offers the service of cloud computing. To achieve the service of cloud computing, the most common utilized communication protocol is Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP). In order to assure the information security and data integrity, Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) and Secure Shell (SSH) are the most common adoption. In a traditional on-premise application deployment

model, the sensitive data of each enterprise continues to reside within the enterprise boundary and is subject to its physical, logical and personnel security and access control policies. However, in cloud computing, the enterprise data is stored outside the enterprise boundary, at the Service provider end. Consequently, the service provider must adopt additional security checks to ensure data security and prevent breaches due to security vulnerabilities in the application or through malicious employees. This involves the use of strong encryption techniques for data security and fine-grained authorization to control access to data. Cloud service providers such as Amazon, the Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2) administrators do not have access to customer instances and cannot log into the Guest OS. EC2 Administrators with a business need are required to use their individual cryptographically strong Secure Shell (SSH) keys to gain access to a host. All such accesses are logged and routinely audited. While the data at rest in Simple Storage Service (S3) is not encrypted by default, users can encrypt their data before it is uploaded to Amazon S3, so that it is not accessed or tampered with by any unauthorized party [3].

Data Privacy:

The data privacy is also one of the key concerns for Cloud computing. A privacy steering committee should also be created to help make decisions related to data privacy. Requirement: This will ensure that your organization is prepared to meet the data privacy demands of its customers and regulators. Data in the cloud is usually globally distributed which raises concerns about jurisdiction, data exposure and privacy. Organizations stand a risk of not complying with government policies as would be explained further while the cloud vendors who expose sensitive information risk legal liability. Virtual co-tenancy of sensitive and non-sensitive data on the same host also carries its own potential risks[2].

Data Integrity:

Data corruption can happen at any level of storage and with any type of media, So Integrity

monitoring is essential in cloud storage which is critical for any data center. Data integrity is

easily achieved in a standalone system with a single database. Data integrity in such a system is maintained via database constraints and transactions. Transactions should follow ACID (atomicity, consistency, isolation and durability) properties to ensure data integrity. Most databases support ACID transactions and can preserve data integrity. Data generated by cloud computing services are kept in the clouds. Keeping data in the clouds means users may lose control of their data and rely on cloud operators to enforce access control.

Data Location:

In general, cloud users are not aware of the exact location of the datacenter and also they do not have any control over the physical access mechanisms to that data. Most well-known cloud service providers have datacenters around the globe. In many a cases, this can be an issue. Due to compliance and data privacy laws in various countries, locality of data is of utmost importance in many enterprise architecture. For example, in many EU and South America countries, certain types of data cannot leave the country because of potentially sensitive information. In addition to the issue of local laws, there's also the question of whose jurisdiction the data falls under, when an investigation occurs. Next in the complexity chain are distributed systems. In a distributed system, there are multiple databases and multiple applications.

In order to maintain data integrity in a distributed system, transactions across multiple data sources need to be handled correctly in a fail safe manner. This can be done using a central global transaction manager. Each application in the distributed system should be able to participate in the global transaction via a resource manager.

Data Availability:

Data Availability is one of the prime concerns of mission and safety critical organizations. When keeping data at remote systems owned by others,

data owners may suffer from system failures of the service provider. If the Cloud goes out of operation, data will become unavailable as the data depends on a single service provider. The Cloud application needs to ensure that enterprises are provided with service around the clock. This involves making architectural changes at the application and infrastructural levels to add scalability and high availability. A multi-tier architecture needs to be adopted, supported by a load- balanced farm of application instances, running on a variable number of servers. Resiliency to hardware/software failures, as well as to denial of service attacks, needs to be built from the ground up within the application. At the same time, an appropriate action plan for business continuity (BC) and disaster recovery (DR) needs to be considered for any unplanned emergencies.

Challenges in security in cloud computing:

Cloud computing environment are multi domain environment in which each domain can use different security, privacy and trust requirement and potentially employ various mechanism, interface and semantics. We describe some challenges in cloud computing

VII. Several approaches for security in cloud computing

After the brief literature survey we explain the several kind of approach for security in cloud computing such that are:

Strong authentication framework:

A strong user authentication framework for cloud computing with many security features, such as identity management, mutual authentication, session key agreement between the users and the cloud server, and user friendliness (i.e., password change phase). The term, strong two factor signifies one factor in „something you know“ (password) and two factors in „something you have“ (smartcard and *OOB*).

Identity based authentication for cloud computing:

Authentication is necessary in Cloud Computing. SSL Authentication Protocol is of low efficiency for Cloud services and users. we presented an identity based authentication for cloud computing, based on the identity-based hierarchical model for cloud computing (IBHMCC) and corresponding encryption and signature schemes. Being certificate-free, the authentication protocol aligned well with demands of cloud computing. Performance analysis indicated that the authentication protocol is more efficient and lightweight than SAP, especially the more lightweight user side. This aligned well with the idea of cloud computing to allow the users with an average or low-end platform to outsource their computational tasks to more powerful servers.

Privacy-preserving digital identity management:

We have proposed an approach to the verification of digital identity for cloud platforms. Our approach uses efficient cryptographic protocols and matching techniques to address heterogeneous naming. We plan to extend this work in several directions. The first direction is to investigate the delegation of identity attributes from clients to CSPs. Delegation would allow a CSP, called the source CSP, to invoke the services of another CSP, called the receiving CSP, by passing to it the identity attributes of the client. However the receiving CSP must be able to verify such identity attributes in case it does not trust the source CSP. One possibility would be to allow the receiving CSP to directly interact with the client; however the source CSP may not be willing to allow the client to know the CSPs it uses for offering its services. Therefore protocols are needed able to address three requirements: confidentiality of business relations among the various CSPs, user privacy, and strength of identity verification. The second direction is the investigation of unlink ability techniques. Our approach does not require that the values of the identity attributes only used for identity verification be disclosed to the CSPs; also our approach allows the user to use pseudonyms when interacting with the CSPs, if the CSP policies allow

the use of pseudonyms and the user is interested in preserving his/her anonymity.

Mutual authentication scheme:

Mutual authentication scheme to minimize the cloud computing security risk such as man-in-middle attack, identity theft, side channel attack and phishing attack. This scheme provides a robust and trustworthy mutual authentication between cloud user and cloud service provider communicate over the internet. It has good efficiency and suitable for cloud computing.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Cloud service providers need to inform their customers on the level of security that they provide on their cloud. In this paper, we first discussed various models of cloud computing, security issues Data security is major issue for Cloud Computing. There are several other security challenges including security aspects of network and virtualization. New security techniques need to be developed and older security techniques needed to be radically tweaked to be able to work with the clouds architecture.

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